

**Empowering
Europe's Data
Future**

D3.1 CONNECTING TO THE HPC NETWORK

29/01/2025

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PARTNERS

D3.1 CONNECTING TO THE HPC NETWORK

Work package	WP3. #compute - The computational component of NOUS
Task	T3.1. Leveraging the HPC Network and its resources for the NOUS
Due date	31/01/2025
Submission date	29/01/2025
Deliverable lead	ARCTUR
Version	1.0
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Abstract	We have observed a growing interest in demand for heterogeneous compute and storage resources, distributed across various geographical locations, working together in a federated manner. A unified platform like NOUS can enhance accessibility, offer greater elasticity, reduce response times, and optimize the use of these underlying resources. We examine current trends from both the perspective of infrastructure providers and end users, with a particular focus on cloud infrastructures that include high-performance computing (HPC) as a key resource. Through a detailed analysis of selected aspects of Cloud-HPC interoperability and similar federated infrastructure setups, several research and innovation challenges are identified, and recommendations and guidelines for the NOUS platform are defined.
Keywords	High Performance Computing, Data Spaces, Cloud Computing

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	01/09/2024	Initial document with introduction	Tomislav Šubić
0.2	01/10/2024	HPC Network integration	Tomislav Šubić, Matevž Skender
0.3	20/10/2024	Authorization and Authentication	Stavros Papamokos, Evangelos Raptis
0.4	12/11/2024	Containers	Tomislav Šubić, Matevž Skender
0.5	17/11/2024	Data	Panagiotis Dimitrakis, Konstantinos Ralis
0.6	05/12/2024	All sections update	Tomislav Šubić
0.7	05/01/2025	Revision of the format	Carolina Villoria
0.8	14/01/2025	Revision of the content	Alberto Montero
1.0	29/01/2025	Final version of the document	Tomislav Šubić

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the work on deliverable “D2.1 Gap analysis and requirements”, we already covered a lot of topics which overlap with this deliverable, especially in the sections about interacting with HPC and Quantum computers. Here we expand that research, while focusing on HPC, steps we need to take and technologies we need to consider to successfully connect the NOUS platform to HPC resources. We consider the motivation and current state of the art, what issues we face and what solutions are available. We mapped the HPC resources inside the consortium and compared their setup to EuroHPC systems.

To ensure a robust and resilient NOUS platform that will cater to the needs of the users and chosen use cases, we need to consider several important factors. We identified the needs of the NOUS use cases, which can be summarized as a set diverse workflows that require a hybrid and heterogeneous computing system that adapts the resource usage depending on the computation. The NOUS platform which supports such a workflow needs to firstly enable the basic services like authentication and authorization, a unified storage system and data transfer layers. After that it needs to develop a cloud computing platform which makes use of orchestration tools like Kubernetes, which will talk to HPC systems through Interfaces that support SLURM, be that some custom tools and solutions, or just using the SLURM REST API.

It is also important to listen to our users and consider their background; the interfaces need to be intuitive and simple, with familiar graphical user interfaces, but with customization options for advanced users.

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ABBREVIATIONS

HPC	High Performance Computing
CC	Cloud Computing
HSM	Hierarchical Storage Management
MPI	Message Passing Interface
IDP	Identity Providers
SP	Service Providers
SSO	Single Sign-On
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
PaaS	Platform as a Service
SaaS	Software as a Service
SLURM	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management
VM	Virtual Machine

1. INTRODUCTION AND STATE OF THE ART

To understand the HPC and Cloud spectrum, we must analyze the fundamental changes in computing technology. The emergence of large-scale commercial cloud platforms and the economic and technological obstacles linked to the evolution of semiconductor technology have shifted the paradigm of computing more towards Cloud computing.

When considering technologies to integrate into the NOUS platform, it is important to distinguish the difference between High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Cloud computing.

High-Performance Computing (HPC) utilizes supercomputers and large computing clusters to address complex problems and manage data-intensive tasks at speeds far surpassing those of traditional computers. These systems are specifically engineered to process vast amounts of data and perform millions of calculations simultaneously, harnessing parallel processing to deliver exceptional performance in demanding computational environments. Essentially, an HPC system consists of interconnected computers that work together to efficiently execute large-scale computations, enabling the effective handling of intricate tasks.

Cloud computing is the provision of computing services, including storage, processing power, and applications over the internet rather than relying on local servers or personal devices. It enables users to access and utilize resources on-demand from any location with internet connectivity, providing flexibility and scalability. This model allows organizations and individuals to leverage various services without the need for significant investments in or maintenance of physical hardware. Additionally, cloud computing is more cost-effective [2].

We distinguish several different Cloud types:

Public cloud: It refers to major commercial cloud providers like Amazon Web Services (AWS), Google Cloud, or Microsoft Cloud, which offer various services such as IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service), PaaS (Platform as a Service), and SaaS (Software as a Service) to numerous customers. Clients share computing, storage, and networking resources in a manner that is "virtually" isolated from one another.

Private Cloud: Typically located on-premises, meaning within the organization's physical space, it provides computing services and resources to the company's employees or partners. It uses similar technologies to those found in public clouds but is tailored to meet the organization's specific requirements. Since resources are limited, smart scheduling is crucial to efficiently allocate private cloud resources to applications while ensuring deadlines are met. An HPC (High-Performance Computing) data center can be likened to a private cloud, offering necessary resources to students and researchers from the universities and institutions that helped establish it.

Hybrid Cloud: In this scenario, the cloud infrastructure is made up of multiple cloud environments combined to create a hybrid cloud. While these clouds remain distinct, they can be integrated as needed for specific applications at certain times. A common example is when the private cloud requires additional capacity and "bursts" workloads to another cloud. Often driven by looming deadlines for resource-intensive applications, the ability to seamlessly extend HPC resources by bursting to the public cloud is a critical factor, especially as more organizations adopt cloud-computing environments.

There is also another type which already hints at some technology overlap and interoperability, the **HPC Cloud**, which refers to HPC resources provided by cloud providers for running HPC applications. Recent research has focused on evaluating the cost-effectiveness of transitioning resource-intensive applications from on-premises systems to public cloud platforms. The simplest implementation of HPC Cloud can be achieved by creating virtual servers in the cloud and installing a Message Passing Interface (MPI) library, such as OpenMPI, in cluster mode. HPC applications which use MPI to parallelize their computations can then use those resources efficiently and with minimal adjustments.

The current state of the art in Cloud and HPC interoperability is characterized by diverse approaches that address the specific needs of different use cases. The trend is moving towards hybrid and federated infrastructures that integrate both HPC and Cloud resources, however, achieving seamless integration and ensuring secure and efficient operation in these complex environments is a significant challenge that requires ongoing research and innovation efforts.

Combined HPC and Cloud computing adoption is growing, where now even the popular Cloud providers like Amazon (AWS), Microsoft (Azure) and Google (Google Cloud) have recognized the HPC market and offer some type of HPC tailored service alongside its Cloud services.

FIGURE 1. GOOGLE CLOUD HPC ARCHITECTURE.

However, considering their published documentation and reference architectures, they focus on either pure HPC computing services, or pure Cloud Computing services, with no customized services that combine both HPC and Cloud Computing in a collaborative manner, where one could use a heterogeneous set of resources for a single workflow. This niche should be a focus of the NOUS platform.

Many users have started adopting Cloud computing for their HPC workloads. Cloud deployments can better handle surges in compute demand and are easy to use, considering that, some users are not concerned by the performance loss when comparing Cloud to bare-metal HPC. On the other hand, there are other negative considerations, data security and data movement, and usually higher cost for on-demand Cloud services. Cloud providers often do not guarantee other performance metrics, like network bandwidth and latency, storage IO, which can be throttled to ensure fair sharing of those common resources by users, and to enable billing of those resources separately. These and other factors tend to also contribute to hidden costs associated with popular cloud providers, where automatic scaling, high data or traffic volumes, or forgotten virtual machines can cause significant unexpected extra costs. On the other hand,

We believe that these solutions which tend to offer a virtual HPC environment inside a Cloud are not the correct way forward. To think of the next iteration of Cloud and HPC interoperability inside the NOUS project, we need to find a way to offer users to seamlessly launch their computational workflows in a platform that truly combines Cloud and HPC, using the most appropriate resources for a given use case, but also keeping the other parts of the system like storage and network easy to use and efficient. Another benefit of such a platform is that smaller HPC clusters, whether private or public, which tend to be underutilized, could be included to boost their cost-effectiveness.

Current users are not only researchers and engineers, but also other types of users like business analysts and similar who use various available software tools instead of directly programming the HPC. With that, a trend is emerging for HPC providers to offer better and more intuitive interfaces for accessing the HPC. Traditionally, HPC has been used via the command line, but nowadays, web interfaces like Jupyter Notebooks, OpenOnDemand [10] have gained in popularity.

This trend reflects a broader shift aimed at making HPC resources more accessible to a wider audience, including those without extensive technical expertise, by the EuroHPC-JU. Web interfaces provide intuitive, graphical environments that simplify complex workflows, enabling users to manage jobs, monitor system performance, and analyze data without the steep learning curve associated with CLIs. These interfaces also facilitate remote access, allowing users to interact with HPC systems through standard web browsers, regardless of location or device. Additionally, web-based solutions integrate better with modern tools for visualization, collaboration, and data sharing, further enhancing productivity. This evolution aligns with the growing demand for democratizing access to HPC

systems, ensuring that both expert and non-expert users can leverage advanced computational resources with greater ease and efficiency.

Hyperion Research [6] reports several top inhibitors to HPC Cloud adoption which have remained consistent: data security, data locality and cost. Research in cost analysis between on-premise clusters and cloud computing concluded that the total cost for running scientific workloads is cheaper on premise (HPC) than running in the cloud[16]. For the NOUS platform this must be one of the top priorities when designing system policies and architecture. Raw compute performance was not highlighted as a critical inhibitor.

2. INFRASTRUCTURE REQUIREMENTS FOR USE-CASES

An integral part of the NOUS project is its use cases. They serve as a benchmark and decision-making guide when designing the platform, as the goal is to enable their execution as efficiently as possible. While all use cases share the need for all three NOUS components; computation, data and edge, some focus more on certain components. Use case #2 - Energy Prediction and Energy Data Lifecycle Management, led by PPC. For PPC to fully leverage the NOUS framework within this use case it must address the computational demands of two key applications: energy prediction and energy data lifecycle management. These applications necessitate robust computational power, high-speed data transfer, and advanced data management capabilities to achieve efficiency, accuracy, and reliability.

The energy prediction task is computationally intensive, requiring the processing of vast amounts of historical energy and weather data, along with real-time sensor inputs and future weather forecasts. To support this application, PPC needs access to HPC systems with high-performance processors, GPUs, and memory architectures capable of handling complex algorithms and machine learning models in real time. These systems must support parallel processing and provide low-latency communication between compute nodes to accelerate the prediction processes. Scalability is critical, as the volume and variety of data will grow with increased sensor deployment and expanding operational territories. Efficient queueing systems for job management are also essential, ensuring that resource-intensive tasks like predictive modeling can run without delays, even under high demand.

For the energy data lifecycle management application, HPC infrastructure must facilitate the centralized processing of data originating from multiple isolated systems, such as ERP, procurement, and production systems. This involves ingesting, cleaning, and integrating disparate datasets into a unified repository. The infrastructure must support high-throughput data pipelines and offer sufficient storage capacity to accommodate the growing volume of customers, suppliers, production, and energy data. High-performance storage solutions with tiered architectures can ensure fast retrieval and secure archiving of sensitive data, while adhering to the Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA) triad.

A federated infrastructure that integrates PPC's cloud-based data repositories with HPC resources is essential to achieve seamless data flow and efficient task execution. High-bandwidth networking solutions are required to support data transfer between the cloud and HPC systems, minimizing latency and avoiding bottlenecks during real-time data analysis. Standardized interfaces for data exchange and management are necessary to simplify integration and provide consistent access to all datasets.

Given the sensitivity of customer and operational data, the infrastructure must incorporate robust security measures. Hardware-based encryption, secure containerization, and compliance with industry standards are crucial to protect data during transit and processing. Blockchain solutions for audit trails could enhance trustworthiness, particularly in cross-organizational data sharing scenarios.

For predictive and analytical tasks, PPC requires platforms capable of running advanced AI and machine learning algorithms. Federated learning infrastructure must ensure secure and decentralized model training, enabling PPC to leverage data from multiple sources while preserving data privacy. Optimized HPC environments can provide the computational power needed for these advanced tasks, reducing the time to insight and improving decision-making accuracy.

By addressing these infrastructure needs, PPC can efficiently harness the potential of HPC systems for its data-intensive applications, enabling predictive accuracy, operational efficiency, and enhanced data management to support its ongoing digital transformation.

Other use cases could also benefit from a HPC connection, but the concrete requirements will be defined at a later stage of the project.

3. MAPPING THE HPC INFRASTRUCTURE

The NOUS platform will develop tools and frameworks to connect to HPC systems. As mentioned, these systems differ greatly in hardware and software, with different access mechanisms and policies. A standardized abstraction layer must be developed to facilitate the connection to multiple HPC systems. In this section we explore the EuroHPC systems and HPC infrastructure available within the NOUS consortium. This will give us an idea of the technical setup of these systems so that we can start developing our HPC connector software in that direction.

3.1. EUROHPC SYSTEMS OVERVIEW

The EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (JU) is a collaborative effort between the European Union, European countries, and private partners to establish a world-class supercomputing infrastructure in Europe. This initiative has led to the deployment of several supercomputers across the EU, each tailored to cater to diverse scientific and industrial applications. These systems aim to provide significantly increased computing power to European HPC users, enabling advancements in fields such as artificial intelligence, data analytics, medicine, climate change research, and materials science. They are typically built on modular architectures, encompassing multiple partitions with varying configurations to address the needs of different applications, including CPU-based, GPU-accelerated, data-centric, and cloud-oriented workloads. These systems prioritize high-performance computing while incorporating energy-efficient designs and open-source software solutions to support a wide range of scientific disciplines.

EuroHPC supercomputers are categorised as either pre-exascale or petascale, meaning they are designed to achieve very high levels of performance. Pre-exascale systems aim for a sustained performance of at least 150 petaflops, while petascale systems fall in the range of 1-100 petaflops.

Most systems are built with modular architectures, incorporating different partitions with distinct configurations to address the requirements of diverse applications.

These include:

- CPU-based partitions: These partitions primarily use x86 CPUs from Intel or AMD.
- GPU-accelerated partitions: These partitions incorporate GPUs, mainly from NVIDIA, to accelerate specific workloads like AI and machine learning.
- FPGA partitions: Some systems, like MeluXina, include partitions equipped with FPGAs alongside GPUs.
- Data-centric partitions: These partitions focus on handling data-intensive workloads and often utilise large memory configurations ("fat nodes").
- Cloud partitions: These partitions leverage cloud technologies and typically use Ceph storage to manage Virtual Machines.

Other common characteristics include high-performance storage in the form of state-of-the-art, multi-tiered storage solutions to meet the capacity and performance demands of modern applications. Lustre is the predominant file system used, while Ceph storage is commonly employed for cloud partitions.

These systems also rely on InfiniBand HDR (100 or 200) for the networking fabric, ensuring fast communication between nodes. EuroHPC systems are connected to the pan-European research network GÉANT with at least 100 Gbps links, enabling fast data transfer and collaboration.

These supercomputers support various programming models and tools including C, C++, Fortran compilers, OpenMP for multicore programming, MPI for multi-node communication, and CUDA, OpenACC, and OpenMP offloading for accelerator programming. Most of the systems utilize containerisation technologies like Singularity to provide application isolation, security, and portability.

As expected, SLURM is the primary scheduler used in several EuroHPC systems. It is explicitly mentioned as the scheduler for the following systems:

- Leonardo: Hosted by CINECA in Italy, Leonardo is one of the three EuroHPC pre-exascale systems.

- MareNostrum5: Hosted by Barcelona Supercomputing Centre is a pre-exascale EuroHPC supercomputer
- Deucalion: Located in Portugal and hosted by the Minho Advanced Computing Centre (MACC), Deucalion is a petascale system.
- Discoverer: Hosted by the Bulgarian National Centre for Supercomputing Applications, Discoverer is another petascale system.
- Vega: Situated in Slovenia and hosted by the Institute of Information Science (IZUM), Vega is also a petascale system.
- Lumi : A petascale supercomputer located at the CSC data center in Kajaani, Finland.
- Karolina: A petascale system hosted by IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center in Czech Republic also uses SLURM.
- MeluXina: A petascale system, hosted in Luxembourg and operated by LuxConnect

The repeated selection of SLURM across these diverse EuroHPC systems suggests its prominence as a robust and widely adopted workload manager within the European HPC landscape. The NOUS platform should consider this information as vital when designing protocols for HPC Network interoperability. The infrastructure inside the consortium – like Arctur’s HPC infrastructure which can be used for testing, is also running on SLURM.

3.2. EUROHPC SYSTEM ACCESS

The access to EuroHPC system is facilitated is governed by the [EuroHPC JU Access Policy](#). The [EuroHPC - Access to Our Supercomputers](#) page has up to date information about the running Access Calls, timeline, resource allocations and eligibility conditions. For the NOUS project, the most appropriate is the [EuroHPC JU Call for Proposals for Development Access](#). The Development Access Call is designed for projects focusing on code and algorithm development, and also includes the MeluXina system. MeluXina is important for NOUS, since it is the only one that offers access to the system via the SLURM REST API, discussed later.

3.3. NOUS CONSORTIUM HPC RESROUCES

ARCTUR has extensive experience building, managing and providing HPC services. As an integrated HPC company, it manages its own Data Center Facility (DCF) and its own hardware and software infrastructure. Arctur also provides HPC consulting, solution development and user training with community outreach as part of the EuroCC initiative.

ARCTURs infrastructure consist of a hyperconverged system, which includes various components and can adapt to any use case. It consists of a classical HPC cluster, powered by Rocky Linux and SLURM, which is a similar setup used by the EuroHPC systems.

The HPC system consists of computing nodes equipped with 256-512GB of memory, 28-core Intel CPUs or 96-core AMD CPUs depending on the partition. Arctur also has a partition with NVIDIA GPUs capable of AI and fast data processing.

During this task, Arctur tested and implemented the SLURM REST API in its HPC cluster, which can be one of the main ways of connecting the HPC cluster to the NOUS platform. Arctur also tested and implemented support for various container technologies, which will be discussed in section 6.

Inside the consortium, HPE has also committed to providing computational resources. As an established infrastructure provider, HPE can provide various bare metal or cloud resources in the form of Virtual Machines (VM). This offers a great opportunity to have 2 different HPC providers and systems within the consortium connected to the NOUS platform. Arctur’s HPC system can act as a system like the standard EuroHPC clusters, while HPE’s resources will provide an opportunity for configuring and deploying a customized HPC solution where all necessary NOUS software components can be installed.

4. SYSTEM-LEVEL POLICY REQUIREMENTS

Security concerns and issues arise when federated Cloud and HPC infrastructures connect resources across different security domains, necessitating the transfer of sensitive data like personal information or trade secrets. Ensuring data confidentiality involves managing security measures across all sites, establishing trust mechanisms, and actively managing security. These challenges require both policy-level actions and technical solutions to safeguard data and ensure secure collaboration between organizations.

The NOUS platform will bring together resources across various geographic locations and security domains, necessitating cross-organizational data transfers. Using these resources for workflows with strict confidentiality or security needs (such as protecting personal data or intellectual property) requires a reassessment of existing security approaches applied in traditional cloud platforms. This involves active management of security measures to ensure harmonized protection levels across locations and the implementation of trust-building mechanisms. While some requirements can be addressed at the policy level, others demand targeted technical solutions.

For example, establishing end-to-end security for workflow or cloud service execution is essential. While cloud environments often use virtualization for secure operations, HPC systems typically avoid such methods due to efficiency concerns and high isolation costs, which can be seen when examining EuroHPC systems. This challenge intensifies in the NOUS platforms and infrastructures with diverse and heterogeneous computing resources, which may vary in support for Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs). Middleware solutions, in collaboration with scheduling systems, will need to address these security demands in the future. Additionally, deploying secure workloads and software components across distributed systems will require a reliable standardized process – one such solution is through containerized applications that adhere to established security standards, such as container encryption.

Trust can be further bolstered by implementing auditing mechanisms for distributed workflows, potentially through blockchain-based solutions for generating transparent audit trails. Another area of concern is data compliance. As data crosses organizational and possibly national boundaries, maintaining adherence to regulatory, organizational, and contractual data requirements becomes increasingly complex. Solutions for data management could support compliance by tagging data repositories and services to align with specific regulatory needs.[1]

4.1. AUTHENTICATION

Through the integration of the NOUS platform to an existing high-performance computing (HPC) network, authentication practices are essential to ensure that only verified users can access sensitive resources. Using federated identity protocols, such as SAML, OpenID Connect, or OAuth 2.0, could allow for consistent identity management across both cloud and HPC environments. Even though the difference in functioning and scope between cloud and HPC systems is significant, federated identity authentication makes sure that user identities are managed consistently and commonly between these two systems.

This enables single sign-on (SSO), letting users authenticate with a single set of credentials, thus streamlining access while reducing the risk of security vulnerabilities. Through SSO, users would only have to sign in once and seamlessly and securely carry and pass on their identity between the NOUS platform and HPC system throughout their entire workload(s).

Additionally, given the possibly very sensitive and critical nature of the data involved in these workloads, multi-factor authentication (MFA) should be enforced for enhanced security, especially for remote access scenarios, to minimise the likelihood of a security breach due to stolen credentials and enable traceability of security incidents.

SSH key management is another important factor. If SSH should be used, then a security policy around the protocol must be set up to amplify its resistance to possible security issues and enforce cautious and secure use of it from the users. This includes, but is not limited to, using state-of-the-art encryption algorithms when generating keys, using rotating keys by setting expiration dates on generated keys, generating and coupling keys with certificates, setting up a Certificate Authority (CA), disallowing password login via SSH etc.

To provide users with seamless access to the diverse services available within the NOUS platform, authentication mechanisms must be harmonized and capable of supporting multiple authentication methods. This harmonization is essential for a cohesive user experience, enabling users to access both cloud and HPC resources with minimal friction. For instance, while of course SSH remains the standard for authenticating access to HPC resources, as it offers robust security and compatibility with existing HPC infrastructure, newer authentication technologies, such as OpenID Connect (OIDC), are increasingly popular due to their flexibility and support for web-based, distributed systems.

OIDC enhances the user experience for cloud services by allowing single sign-on (SSO) and token-based authentication, which is well-suited for modern cloud applications. By incorporating both SSH and OIDC within a unified authentication framework, the NOUS platform can offer users a streamlined access process tailored to the needs of each type of service. This approach not only improves usability but also strengthens security by ensuring that each resource—whether cloud or HPC—is protected by the most suitable authentication method.

4.1.1. AUTHORIZATION

Implementing the tried and tested role-based access control (RBAC) scheme allows permissions to be assigned based on user roles, such as researcher or administrator, and ensures adherence to permissions assigned to each role. This limits users' access to only what is necessary for their roles. Such an approach allows system administrators and security operators to easily assign and revoke permissions to users on demand and always have a summary of which users can do specific actions within the system.

Additionally, applying access control lists (ACLs) can further help further segment data and resources, restricting sensitive data to only those users or services that absolutely require access. Access control lists can greatly simplify the granting and revocation of security attributes of resources. Here, the term 'resources' can be freely interpreted, ranging from files and services hosted on the NOUS system and/or HPC network, to computing hosts and hardware.

To effectively apply the required authorization policies to the system, a robust policy enforcement mechanism is essential. This mechanism should encompass and enforce all authorization configurations comprehensively, ensuring consistent application of security policies across the system. Additionally, it should be optimized for quick access and efficient querying, both in terms of response time and computational resource usage, while remaining highly secure and trustworthy. The mechanism must be invoked reliably whenever a user attempts to log in, access resources, or perform any action, ensuring that all access requests are thoroughly validated in real time. Lastly, to enable simple and transparent auditing and analysis, each authorization request along with its outcome should always be logged in a verbose manner and in a secure location where only persons with the appropriate permissions are allowed to access them.

4.1.2. IDENTITY AND SERVICE PROVIDERS

A typical authentication and authorization (AA) architecture designed for cloud and HPC interoperability consists of two essential components: Identity Providers (IdPs) and Service Providers (SPs). The IdPs are tasked with verifying user identities and issuing secure authentication tokens that serve as proof of identity. These tokens contain credentials or claims that the SPs rely on to manage access to their services. In complex, distributed cloud and HPC environments, IdPs and SPs are frequently located in different geographic regions, which enhances the system's scalability and resilience. This geographic distribution helps balance user demands across multiple locations, enabling reliable, low-latency access and providing redundancy to ensure continuity even in the event of a localized outage.

A key challenge in implementing this AA framework is establishing secure, trustworthy relationships between the IdPs and SPs. These trust relationships are foundational, as SPs must be confident that the tokens provided by IdPs are legitimate and meet strict security requirements. This challenge becomes even more important when considering highly sensitive services, such as those granting direct access to HPC resources or processing confidential data, where a high level of assurance and security is mandatory. Here, strong cryptographic protocols, secure token formats, and robust mutual authentication practices must be used to verify identities and maintain data integrity.

By addressing these challenges and implementing a robust AA framework, the NOUS platform can provide a secure, efficient, and user-friendly experience for researchers, scientists, and other stakeholders.

FIGURE 2. DIAGRAM OF THE AUTHENTICATION AND AUTHORIZATION FRAMEWORK.

A summary of the AA framework is given in the diagram which highlights the flow between key components such as Users, Identity Providers (IdPs), Authentication Mechanisms, Authorization protocols, Service Providers (SPs), and the underlying resources (HPC and Cloud).

Users are authenticated by IdPs through identity protocols, using available authentication mechanisms. Based on the defined Policies, the IdPs verify users and issues tokens which are used as proof of identify on the NOUS platform. Service Providers can validate these user tokens and communicate with services such as HPC resources or Cloud services, where they use different authentication mechanisms. HPC users are usually authenticated though SSH but can then issue tokens to be used for the SLURM REST API.

This architecture ensures secure, streamlined, and efficient integration across distributed environments.

4.2. DATA SECURITY AND PRIVACY POLICIES

As identified in the introduction, data security is a major obstacle that prevents many high-performance computing (HPC) sites and users from fully embracing cloud computing services. This concern encompasses a wide range of issues. Cloud service providers (CSPs) have responded to various data protection regulations worldwide by obtaining certifications such as FedRAMP, GDPR, and HIPAA. At a technical level, data security refers to the security capabilities and certifications that CSPs are integrating into their platforms for secure computing and storage. However, security certifications still do not guarantee that the data will be protected, only that certain efforts have been made to ensure that.

In certain segments of the HPC market, some data sets, such as financial data, seismic data, and software subject to export control for national security reasons, are not allowed to cross state or national borders. As a result, CSPs are taking steps to enable users to choose the computing and storage location to comply with such regulations, but this is still not a widely available feature, and no guarantees are made that the uploaded data won't be replicated to another site at another location for backup or similar. This added flexibility to control the location of instances and designate where an application runs and data is stored allows applications with strict data laws to be legally deployed in the cloud.

However, data security involves more than just technical aspects. There is an intangible bias where data stored in one's own data center may feel more secure than in a third-party data center, regardless of the actual security features of either data center. Addressing this perception of on-premises data being more secure is more challenging. This sense of security can outweigh the security protocols of a cloud-based solution, numerous studies showing that users tend to keep some data on-premises, even when cloud platforms have robust security capabilities [6].

When talking about data security, there is also similar concern of data locality. For many users, the data sets needed to run their applications are large and growing rapidly. The process of moving these large data sets can often take longer than simply running the applications on-premises. This is particularly true for emerging AI workloads,

where the training data for neural networks must be extensive to allow for the development of highly accurate models. Platforms that want to enable HPC and Cloud interoperability need to consider data transfer speed and efficiency, including upload time, data volumes and easy access once on the platform. Cloud providers have started to address this challenge by introducing "fast pipe" or data upload solutions that enable large data sets to be transferred to the cloud at an acceptable rate. AWS Snowball is one example of such a service.

However, data locality remains a concern for many organizations. As data set sizes continue to grow with the increasing adoption of artificial intelligence, big data, and HPC applications, the need for high-speed data ingress, egress, and movement is becoming critical for a growing number of users. While CSPs have been working to address these issues, their solutions have been reactive rather than proactive, as data set sizes and data locality requirements continue to evolve and increase in complexity.

4.3. DATA MANAGEMENT AND TRANSFER

Efficient data management and transfer mechanisms are critical for the NOUS platform to function as an interconnected and federated High-Performance Computing ecosystem. It is critical, as the NOUS platform must handle diverse workloads, integrate orchestrate and exploit edge and cloud resources, and ensure the secure and seamless flow of data between geographically distributed nodes.

4.3.1. PHYSICAL STORAGE ON HPC SYSTEMS

It is common that HPC platforms like NOUS rely on a combination of high-speed and high-capacity storage solutions, to be able to meet diverse workload and application requirements. Disk-based storage arrays, in RAID configuration, provide reliability, redundancy, and scalability. These arrays can be combined with parallel file systems like Lustre [11] and BeeGFS. Doing so, they will be able to ensure high throughput and efficient data management and sharing across multiple HPC nodes. For frequently used datasets, solid-state drives (SSDs) are the appropriate choice, as they offer the required low latency and high input/output operations per second, that makes them ideal for caching and fast data access. On the other hand, high-capacity disk drives (HDDs) serve as cost-effective solutions for rarely accessed data and intermediate storage.

For long-term archiving of infrequently used data, tape storage systems remain a popular choice due to their durability and significantly low operational costs compared to others. Technologies like LTO (Linear Tape-Open) offer high storage densities and reliable cold storage for backups or historical datasets. Their existence is common in multi-tier storage architectures, which combine fast and expensive storage like NVMe drives for real-time processing with less expensive options like HDDs and tapes for archival purposes. This type of multi-tiering can meet the required performance of the HPC system and its applications while also maintaining a relative cost efficiency.

The distribution of the data accessible by an HPC platform, as well as the load balancing and fault tolerance are of great importance, and thus storage nodes and clusters play a vital role. Techniques like RAID configurations that were mentioned above, erasure coding, and storage replication can be used to ensure data integrity and enhance reliability. Modular storage solutions also enable scalability, allowing HPC platforms like NOUS to maintain upgrade and expand their storage capacity incrementally, depending on the demand. Local storage on computing nodes can further enhance performance by providing scratch space for temporary data, leading to reduced network dependency during high I/O operations.

4.3.2. ADVANCED DATA MANAGEMENT AND OPTIMIZATION IN HPC SYSTEMS

As mentioned above, an HPC platform, can contain multiple tiers of storage, depending on the corresponding data and thus, on top of the Physical Layer, Hierarchical Storage Management (HSM) solutions are fundamental for optimizing storage resource usage by automatically migrating data between performance tiers. High-performance storage, such as SSD based Lustre systems, are mainly appointed to frequently accessed data, while older or infrequently accessed data is moved to cost-efficient storage tier solutions such as tape archives or cold storage within Ceph. Lustre offers scalability, ensuring that any expansion of the available computational resources will be accompanied by an expansion of the storage system, to match the demand. Ceph on the other hand, offers a robust,

scalable object storage system, suitable for distributed operation. Ceph guarantees data availability and fault tolerance, while also offering compatibility with cloud technologies. This feature can possibly enable NOUS to operate into hybrid and multi-cloud environments. The two storage systems can both be integrated and used interchangeably, depending on the requirements of the application. Ceph can be selected for flexibility, fault tolerance and the capability to handle diverse workloads, while Lustre targets more to high-performance parallel workloads in HPC environments. By leveraging metadata policies, HSM systems can dynamically allocate resources, providing a balance between performance and cost efficiency for NOUS workloads.

The parallel file system, Lustre, as well as others, such as BeeGFS and IBM Storage Scale, offer high throughput and simultaneous access to datasets by multiple compute nodes. They enable the distribution of data across multiple storage devices, enabling faster read/write operations essential for data-intensive tasks like weather simulations or machine learning training. For optimal performance, file system parameters such as stripe size in Lustre should be carefully configured based on workload characteristics.

The NOUS platform targets a wide and diverse user base and thus, an efficient and fair usage of the available resources is required. This can be pursued with the employment of quotas. By defining quotas, administrators can prevent any single user or team from monopolizing high-performance storage (and even computational) resources. For example, each separate research group, company or individual user might be provided with a specific amount of Lustre storage for active projects and Ceph space for archiving. The use of quotas can be achieved with monitoring and resource management tools, such as SLURM, ensuring efficient usage while providing transparency.

The efficient use of the available data storage resources requires an efficient manipulation of the provided and also the generated data, through related policies. Data compression and deduplication are two common and effective policies, used to optimize storage space in HPC systems. Techniques such as GZIP and LZ4 can significantly reduce the size of large datasets. Deduplication is another significant technique for storage usage optimization, as the presence of duplicates is common and poses an accountable storage overhead, especially in platforms where datasets undergo incremental updates or are shared among multiple different projects and users. The capability of NOUS's provided storage system to keep backups and snapshots is also critical for security reasons. Towards this direction, tools like ZFS or Ceph's built in features enable periodic data capture.

For data access optimization, the use of distributed node-level caching using SSDs or even NVMe drives can provide significant performance boost when accessing frequently used datasets. Adding to that, distributed caching systems like Memcached or Redis offer an additional level of optimization by storing metadata in memory.

In such platforms, the use of collaborative data spaces can be proven useful, as it promotes teamwork and boosts research efforts by providing centralized repositories for project-specific data. These spaces can be implemented using shared storage on Lustre or object storage buckets in Ceph, accessible to specific collaborating users across teams.

Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) is another technology which is commonly present in HPC systems. This is related both with data management and transfer, as it aims to reduce latency by bypassing the CPU involvement in data transfers. While often mentioned in HPC documentation, it is a lower layer technology and abstracted through other mechanisms which support standard data transfer protocols, so NOUS should not invest much effort in researching it.

4.3.3. DATA TRANSFER

Data transfer in HPC systems such as NOUS, is highly related to data storage and management. Some concept described above, such as compression or RDMA, when used, lead towards more efficient data transferring. There are, however, additional strategies and tools that can be employed to address significant data transfer challenges.

The incorporation of data staging is one of those. Data staging is practically the preloading of datasets onto HPC storage systems. The automation of data transfer to required high-speed storage (i.e. Lustre-based storage) can be achieved with the use of tools like Globus, or Rsync. Globus, among others, offers a set of services for file transferring, authentication and authorization mechanisms focusing on secure transfers, and incorporates features like

encryption and checkpointing. This transfer can be further optimized by the incorporation of time scheduling policies that prioritize the transfer of large datasets during off-peak hours.

Efficiency in terms of bandwidth usage can also be achieved by the incorporation of incremental data transfers when possible. Rsync is again a tool that is considered very effective for such lightweight synchronization tasks, offering efficient file copying and updating capabilities by transferring only the changes between source and destination. For more bandwidth intensive tasks, multi-threaded transfer can be employed. This can be implemented by tools such as Aspera or GridFTP, that practically utilize multiple parallel streams to accelerate the movement of large datasets, after dividing them into smaller chunks.

To minimize the manual incorporation of such features, the strategy of incorporation premade workflow managers can be followed. Such tools are the Apache Airflow and Pegasus WMS. The NOUS platform, as expressed also from the various use cases that will verify its operation, is required to have the capability of handling live data received through integrated edge devices. Apache NiFi is a tool able to handle live-data ingestion, transformation, and routing. It is mainly installed on the edge side and enables edge devices to share data with the HPC platform nodes, ensuring the successful execution of several common preprocessing tasks such as data filtering, formatting, and aggregation before reaching the main computational node. After reaching the server side, Apache Kafka, a distributed messaging system that can be used to enable real-time data streaming takes the lead and ensures that incoming data streams are processed and routed to the appropriate HPC resources.

4.4. INTEGRATION OF GAIA-X WITH NOUS

Gaia-X is a European initiative which focuses on data and has as a main target the development of a federated data infrastructure [12]. Security can be considered its main priority. Gaia – X seeks to promote innovation through collaboration around Europe and it fully complies with European values and regulations. NOUS is also an under-development European platform that seeks to enhance research through collaboration and by providing the much needed computational resources. Being a European project too, NOUS must fully comply with EU regulations and values. NOUS targets also to be used along with heterogenous data and data received from edge devices, for federated learning applications. So, Gaia-X architecture principles and NOUS goals, that of providing a distributed, high-performance computing infrastructure, completely align. There are several architectural elements of Gaia-X that can be integrated within the NOUS platform.

Gaia-X provides a Trust Framework, which verifies that all the participants comply with legal standards and regulations. That this framework can be adopted by NOUS platform and used as a verification mechanism for all the users and participants. This not only ensures data integrity and usage transparency, but it also guarantees compliance with EU regulations.

Additionally, Gaia-X through the Gaia-X Digital Clearing Houses service (GXDCH), offers automatic validation for compliance with the rules and regulations. GXDC additionally contains a set of optional parameters that can be used, such as the frontend login wizard, the wallet, responsible for the storing of credentials and the Catalogue, responsible for keeping and presenting various listings, such as the service offerings or the participants. That way, with the incorporation of GXDCH, in can be guaranteed that the federated data used throughout NOUS, as well as its computational service, respect the standards of interoperability and technical compatibility, as they have been demonstrated in Gaia – X.

As slightly mentioned above, targeting security, Gaia-X also provides robust and highly secure identity protocols, as well as management protocols. Their integration in NOUS can help manage using authentication tasks which will also guarantee secure access on data and computational services.

Moreover, Gaia – X, through the communication and exchange protocols that implements, allows for standardized and easy communication between different platforms that integrate Gaia-X, promoting seamless interoperability. In general, this interoperability is achieved through open APIs and protocols such as REST or GraphQL. Those protocols can thus be implemented in NOUS, to ease its communication with other external federated ecosystems. Additionally, NOUS platform can benefit, in terms of interoperability, by incorporating the semantic integration techniques that Gaia-X promotes for the alignment of diverse datasets. This type of integration will allow NOUS to execute standardized exchange of data between its various components, (edge, compute, quantum etc.). To verify

this, Gaia-X uses verification tools such as SHACL-based credential validation, which can also be incorporated in NOUS to ensure that all the used services and data comply with Gaia-X standards.

Several projects have successfully implemented Gaia-X ecosystems. HEALTH-X dataLOFT and TEAM-X create secure, sovereign health data spaces using GXFS for healthcare. The Smart Connected Supplier Network (SCSN) supports data sharing in manufacturing, while Gaia-X4 Future Mobility focuses on mobility solutions. Energy data-X facilitates data spaces in Germany's energy sector, and COOPERANTS enhances collaboration in Aeronautics and Space with a digital service infrastructure. The Boot-X project, part of Huawei's Exchange Data Space, provides a Gaia-X-compliant technology stack for data space setups. All those dataspaces can be used in combination with the NOUS platform taking advantage of its HPC resources for computation and simulation.

5. HPC NETWORK INTEGRATION

HPC clusters and software are often very customized, depending on the HPC center needs. Often this means that there are also a lot of software solutions, frameworks and tools developed serving different use cases, but which are also to a certain extent. In this section we explore the many possibilities of connecting to the HPC network, while keeping in mind that the NOUS platform will aim to support the most popular systems and software.

5.1. CLOUD AND HPC RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Traditionally, HPC and cloud infrastructures have taken distinct approaches to managing resources. In HPC environments, resource managers focus on maximizing resource utilization, often allowing significant delays in job start times to prevent overallocation of computing resources and ensure fair resource usage. In contrast, cloud systems prioritize rapid response times and elastic scaling, aiming for efficient use of available hardware. Another key difference lies in workload patterns: HPC systems typically handle fewer, longer-running, large-scale jobs (sometimes a single, intensive job), whereas cloud platforms often support many smaller microservices that may run briefly, making setup and teardown speeds crucial.

As hardware becomes more diverse, such as servers equipped with accelerators like GPUs, both HPC and cloud resource management face added complexity. For platforms combining HPC and cloud resources, this diversity implies the coexistence of different resource management systems. In federated infrastructures, coordinating resource managers across multiple sites can be essential for timely resource access, presenting an opportunity and challenge for collaboration among developers of HPC and Cloud services. Further research and development are needed in orchestrating diverse resource managers for optimal use of HPC and cloud infrastructures, supporting the co-allocation of various resource types. Innovations in this area would also enable HPC cloud bursting, allowing HPC centers to meet peak demands by utilizing cloud resources on an as-needed basis [4].

A central challenge in the NOUS platform will be the unified allocation and accounting of resources. The platform would need to allow resources from multiple organizations to be allocated to services or various use-cases, enabling access to different types of computing resources across locations. At the same time, users should be able to monitor resource usage centrally without needing to gather data manually from various providers, some of them using proprietary systems. Achieving this requires standardized, secure interfaces and mechanisms for sharing information on resource allocation and usage. NOUS should invest in developing such a system, which offers centralized resource allocation, accounting and monitoring capabilities.

SLURM (Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management) has emerged as the most widely used resource manager for HPC systems, particularly among the systems listed in the TOP500 supercomputers, but more importantly, it is also the most popular resource manager on the EuroHPC systems. Its popularity stems from its robust scalability, flexibility, and open-source nature, making it well-suited for managing the complex workloads typical of HPC environments. SLURM efficiently handles job scheduling and resource allocation, enabling optimal use of computing resources across a wide variety of architectures. Its modular design allows customization to meet the specific requirements of diverse HPC systems, ranging from small clusters to the largest supercomputers. Moreover, SLURM's active community and continuous development ensure it stays up to date with advancements in hardware and software technologies, further solidifying its position as the resource manager of choice in the HPC domain. While traditionally HPC users would interact with SLURM via CLI, recently SLURM has published a REST API, which many GUI applications take advantage of to provide better user experience.

NOUS can consider a few different ways of connecting to the HPC Network, which is discussed in the following sections.

5.2. DIRECT SLURM JOB SUBMISSION VIA SSH

One way to connect a Cloud platform running Kubernetes with an HPC system is by allowing Kubernetes containers to submit jobs directly to Slurm via SSH. This method requires SSH credentials or tokens to be mounted into the container. A script within the container would handle copying data to the HPC system, preparing the job, and sub-

mitting it to Slurm using sbatch. The container would manage job statuses (e.g., waiting for completion) using Slurm commands like squeue or sacct.

- Pros: This approach is simple, requires minimal tooling, and provides direct control over Slurm.
- Cons: Managing SSH keys or tokens securely for each container is challenging.

5.3. USING A MESSAGE QUEUE (RABBITMQ OR KAFKA)

In this method, Kubernetes containers send job requests to a message queue, such as RabbitMQ or Kafka, which a listener on the HPC side (external to Kubernetes) processes. The listener receives the job, submits it to Slurm, and updates the queue with job status or notifies the container. The data can either be copied to the HPC by the container or the listening service.

- Pros: This decouples Kubernetes from Slurm, providing flexibility for job management.
- Cons: It requires setting up and maintaining a message queue and listener service.

5.4. USE OF WORKFLOW ORCHESTRATION TOOLS

Workflow orchestration tools can handle Kubernetes-based job scheduling. These custom tools can be set up to trigger jobs when a heavy workload is detected or when the container initiates the workflow. In both cases, the workflow orchestrator sends job requests to an external HPC system like Slurm and manages job dependencies, retries, and status checking.

- Pros: Designed for complex workflows and integrates well with Kubernetes.
- Cons: Extra plugins or integrations may be required to communicate with Slurm.

5.5. JOB DISPATCH VIA DATA TRANSFER SYSTEMS

If the data generated by a Kubernetes container needs processing on an HPC system, a data transfer mechanism like Globus or rsync can be set up. This would move large datasets from Kubernetes to the HPC file system and trigger a Slurm job when new data arrives for processing.

- Pros: This method separates data processing from Kubernetes and automates job dispatch based on incoming data.
- Cons: It requires a robust data transfer system and reliable file system monitoring.

5.6. JOB SCHEDULING BASED ON KUBERNETES EVENTS

Kubernetes event-driven mechanisms like Knative Eventing or KEDA (Kubernetes Event-driven Autoscaler) can trigger Slurm jobs based on specific conditions, such as data volume or CPU/memory usage thresholds. These tools listen for events in Kubernetes and trigger an action (e.g., calling a REST API or submitting a Slurm job) when certain conditions are met. However, continuing calculations from Kubernetes to HPC could be a challenge with this method.

- Pros: It integrates with Kubernetes events to automate job submission.
- Cons: Event thresholds need careful management, and applications must handle continued computation after a graceful shutdown.

5.7. INTEGRATING A BATCH JOB SCHEDULER

A batch job scheduler can translate Kubernetes jobs into HPC workloads and dispatch them to the HPC system. A Kubernetes-Slurm connector can convert Kubernetes job resources into Slurm jobs directly. Tools like Flux, which

can manage both containerized Kubernetes workloads and batch Slurm jobs, or Volcano, which handles job orchestration within Kubernetes and dispatches them to external HPC schedulers, can be used for this.

- Pros: This provides centralized job scheduling for Kubernetes and HPC with seamless job translation.
- Cons: It is complex to set up, and not all jobs can be mapped cleanly to Slurm workloads. Both clusters require installation and configuration.

5.8. SLURM REST API INTEGRATION

When Slurm is configured with a REST API, Kubernetes can interact with Slurm by calling the API endpoints directly. A lightweight client inside the Kubernetes container can communicate with Slurmrest for job submission, status checking, and resource querying.

In short, the Slurm Rest API allows users to interact with Slurm from a standard HTTP REST API, in addition to the command line interface. This does not come enabled in the default SLURM installation but has to be installed and configured by the HPC administrators. Users need to authenticate via SSH and create a JWT token. Using that token they can authenticate against the SLURM REST API.

Pros: Eliminates the need for SSH and manual interaction, providing a clean API-based solution.
Cons: Requires Slurm to have a configured API, and secure API credential management is necessary.

5.9. CLOUD BURSTING

The previous technologies all come from the standpoint on how to expand the Cloud system with HPC. It is also important to consider solutions that have been developed to serve the other case, where HPC systems capabilities are expanded with Cloud computing resources – also known as Cloud bursting. Cloud bursting is a hybrid computing strategy that allows HPC operators to dynamically expand their on-premises infrastructure into a public or private cloud to manage excess computational demand. This approach is particularly advantageous for high-performance computing (HPC) environments, where workloads can vary significantly and the cost of maintaining sufficient on-premises resources to meet peak demands may be prohibitive. With cloud bursting, organizations can tap into cloud resources, even from multiple providers, to handle workload spikes without compromising performance or investing in permanent hardware upgrades. This ensures operational flexibility, cost efficiency, and the ability to scale resources on demand, making it ideal for data-intensive or compute-heavy tasks that experience periodic surges. In cloud bursting we need to consider all the usual factors when talking about heterogeneous computing: network traffic and data transfer to and from different storage systems, software adaptation – our application can't rely on some hardware specific features

SLURM, as one of the most widely used resource managers for HPC systems, has robust support for cloud bursting. It achieves this through its ability to integrate seamlessly with cloud platforms and manage hybrid environments. SLURM can provision and schedule jobs across both on-premises clusters and cloud resources, treating cloud nodes as extensions of the local HPC system. This is made possible through SLURM's robust plugin architecture and configuration options, which allow administrators to define cloud-based compute nodes in a way that they appear as part of the HPC cluster. Jobs can be automatically or manually directed to these cloud resources based on pre-defined policies, workload types, or resource availability.

The process involves dynamic provisioning, where SLURM interfaces with cloud providers to create virtual machines or containers that meet specific job requirements. These virtual instances are then registered with the SLURM controller, allowing them to receive and execute workloads as if they were native to the on-premises cluster. SLURM also supports automatic deprovisioning, where cloud resources are released once they are no longer needed, ensuring cost efficiency by aligning resource usage with demand.

FIGURE 3. CLOUD BURSTING SETUP USING SLURM AND AWS [17].

6. CONTAINER SOLUTIONS

Container technology offers significant advantages for both HPC and cloud environments, enhancing portability, modularity, reproducibility, resource management, and security. Containers encapsulate applications and their dependencies, enabling consistent execution across diverse computing platforms, whether on-premises HPC clusters or various cloud providers. This portability eliminates the need for complex reinstallation procedures and ensures software compatibility, simplifying application deployment and streamlining workflows. Containers also promote modularity by allowing the decomposition of large applications into smaller, independent microservices. This approach enhances scalability, allowing individual components to be scaled as needed, and improves flexibility, simplifying updates and modifications without affecting the entire system. A key advantage of containers is their ability to guarantee consistent execution environments, which enhances the reproducibility of scientific workflows. Reproducibility is crucial for research, ensuring reliable and repeatable results irrespective of the underlying infrastructure. Containers can be effectively managed by orchestration platforms like Kubernetes, which provide tools for resource allocation, scheduling, and scaling. This integration with robust resource management systems streamlines container deployment and operation, optimizing resource utilization and simplifying administration. Furthermore, containers provide a level of isolation that enhances security by preventing privilege escalation, particularly crucial in shared HPC environments. Certain container solutions, like Singularity, incorporate features like root filesystem encryption and cryptographic signing of images to bolster security further. This combination of benefits makes containers increasingly popular in HPC and cloud computing, facilitating efficient, portable, and secure application deployment and execution. In this section we review currently popular and mature container solutions with active development [3][5].

6.1.1. SARUS

Sarus is a container engine developed by the Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS) specifically to address the unique requirements of High-Performance Computing environments. Its primary focus is on delivering secure and scalable container deployments within HPC infrastructures, offering compatibility with Docker images. Sarus is designed to enable users to run Docker-based containers in HPC environments without the need for Docker daemons, providing a more streamlined and secure solution [14].

Sarus is purpose-built for HPC use cases, ensuring both security and scalability. It supports the conversion of Docker images for use in HPC environments, eliminating the need for running Docker daemons. Additionally, Sarus integrates well with common HPC job schedulers such as SLURM, making it an ideal choice for managing large-scale HPC workloads.

Sarus provides direct access to the host filesystem, including shared HPC storage systems such as Lustre. It is designed to work efficiently with HPC-specific networking setups, including Message Passing Interface (MPI) and InfiniBand, ensuring seamless communication for parallel computing. Data transfer is facilitated using existing HPC storage mounts, making it simple to transfer data between containers and the host environment.

6.1.2. APPTAINER

Apptainer is the community-driven continuation of Singularity[15], developed specifically for HPC environments. It retains Singularity's core features while focusing on security, portability, and compatibility with various HPC job schedulers and workflows. Apptainer is designed to be user-friendly and to meet the security standards required for running containers in HPC environments.

Apptainer preserves Singularity's rootless execution model, which ensures that containers run with the same user privileges, maintaining a secure environment. It offers strong integration with MPI, allowing parallel applications to run efficiently. Apptainer also continues to support the Singularity Image Format (SIF), maintaining compatibility with pre-existing Singularity containers and workflows.

Apptainer allows direct access to the host filesystem and mounted directories without requiring special permissions or configurations. It supports native networking and HPC interconnects, such as InfiniBand, and works well

with communication libraries like MPI. Data transfer is simplified using shared filesystems like Lustre and GPFS, allowing easy access and transfer of data between containers and the host system.

6.1.3. SINGULARITY

Singularity is a container solution specifically tailored for HPC environments, with a strong emphasis on security and integration with traditional batch scheduling systems. Its design allows users to run containers without requiring root access, making it a popular choice for security-conscious HPC environments. Singularity enables seamless execution of containerized applications while maintaining user privileges.

One of the standout features of Singularity is its rootless architecture, ensuring that containers run with the same privileges as the user without the need for root daemons. It is fully compatible with MPI and other HPC libraries, enabling efficient execution of parallel applications. Singularity can work directly with Docker images and repositories and integrates easily with traditional HPC job schedulers such as SLURM, PBS, and LSF. Singularity also includes a SLURM plugin that allows SLURM jobs to be natively run within a Singularity container. It also enables access to host resources such as GPUs.

Singularity provides direct access to the host filesystem and mounted directories, eliminating the need for complex volume mount configurations. It supports HPC interconnects such as InfiniBand, crucial for MPI-based applications. Shared filesystems like Lustre and GPFS are natively accessible, enabling seamless data transfers between the host environment and containers.

Singularity and Apptainer are very similar, sometimes used interchangeably in documentation, which often creates confusion. The Singularity project became Apptainer in 2021, after it became part of the Linux Foundation [9]. At the same time, Sylabs, a private company, worked on the existing Singularity project and continued developing it under the same name and as a commercial solution. The community is more in favor of Apptainer.

6.1.4. CHARLIECLOUD

Charliecloud is a lightweight and unprivileged container framework designed for use in HPC environments.[13] It allows users to run containers without requiring root access, simplifying integration with existing HPC workflows. Charliecloud emphasizes simplicity and compliance with HPC security policies, making it an attractive option for users seeking minimalistic containerization solutions.

Charliecloud is designed with a user-space-only execution model, meaning no root access is required for container execution. Its minimalist design prioritizes ease of integration with existing HPC infrastructures. Like other HPC container engines, it natively supports parallel computing libraries such as MPI, ensuring it can handle distributed applications efficiently.

Charliecloud offers direct access to the host filesystem without requiring complex setups. It is fully compatible with HPC networking setups, including InfiniBand, and works well with MPI-based communication. Data transfer is straightforward, utilizing existing HPC shared storage solutions, which makes moving data between containers and the host system simple and efficient.

6.1.5. SHIFTER

Shifter was developed by the National Energy Research Scientific Computing Center (NERSC) to address the limitations of Docker in HPC environments. It is specifically designed to convert Docker images into formats suitable for HPC use, without the need for a Docker daemon. Shifter integrates tightly with HPC job schedulers and distributed file systems, making it a powerful tool for containerized HPC workflows.

Shifter's primary distinction is its ability to convert Docker images for use in HPC without needing a Docker daemon. This makes it highly secure and well-suited for HPC environments. It is designed to work seamlessly with HPC job schedulers and distributed file systems, providing strong integration with NERSC resources and similar HPC facilities.

sShifter integrates well with existing HPC storage systems such as Lustre and GPFS, allowing direct access to data from the host environment. It supports MPI and other communication libraries used in parallel computing, making it ideal for distributed HPC applications. Shared filesystems are used for data access and transfer, ensuring efficient movement of data between containers and the host environment.

6.2. CLOUD EXTENSION SOLUTIONS

Although it is new and serving a niche market, there have been initiatives aiming to develop similar solution to the NOUS platform, where the aim is to offload workloads to other platforms, but are limited for a specific use cases and technologies. Projects like Ligo[7] and EU-funded InterTwin[8] both work on Kubernetes deployment solutions, with a focus on multi-cluster topologies.

Ligo aims to offload workloads to remote clusters without requiring any modifications to Kubernetes or the applications themselves, with an automatic peer-to-peer establishment of resource and service consumption relationships between the clusters.

InterLink is a solution developed within the InterTwin project. It specifically targets Kubernetes applications with tasks to be executed on HPC systems; these can involve complex computations, simulations data processing and other HPC workloads. It also supports running containers on demand with specific computing needs while utilizing lambda-like functions that call on external resources. It targets remote Kubernetes clusters (similar to Ligo) but focuses primarily on the HPC ecosystem by supporting the SLURM scheduler with Apptainer or Singularity. It is not suited for long-running services that require high availability.

Both projects are open source with active git repositories, and while both appear to be early in the development phase, Ligo seems more mature. The obvious limitation is that both solutions assume that the platform is running exclusively on Kubernetes technology. In the NOUS project it is not yet clear what the main underlying technology will be.

In the development phase, the NOUS platform should make a deep dive into these two solutions and try to include parts of Ligo and especially InterLink into its platform, as it seems to have many overlapping features.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable we explored and summarized research on the current state of HPC and Cloud interoperability. We identified key system policy considerations when designing such a system. The partners gathered knowledge and experience with most of the mentioned technologies by running tests and experiments on their infrastructure, which is essential for efficient work on the next tasks. We mapped technologies of EuroHPC systems and Arctur's HPC system to ensure seamless integration with the HPC network within the NOUS platform for testing and development. Since the conducted research and analysis of the different areas necessary to integrate HPC and Cloud systems into the NOUS platform, we recommend the following actions for further research and implementation:

The integration of an authentication and authorization infrastructure enabling seamless identity provisioning across the NOUS platform and connected systems is vital for the user experience while making efforts to ensure best security practices, like multi-factor authentication. AA needs to provide tokens which all the other services on the NOUS platform can validate.

Integrating different types of services inside the NOUS platform with a modular architecture that can accommodate experienced users and CLI tools, as well as beginners who prefer GUI applications like web portals for data transfer and job submission.

The NOUS resource management system which will take care of the resources available to NOUS and communication with external systems needs to be able to talk to SLURM, since it is the industry standard for HPC resource management. This can be achieved via various mechanisms, but the SLURM REST API is most appropriate. We need to explore the development of a hybrid system, which will support diverse workflows and ensure the most appropriate resources for a given computational task. Depending on the rest of the NOUS platform, an alternative solution if to use Kubernetes multi-cluster extension solutions.

Develop a container creation and deployment mechanism that will be tailored for the available HPC hardware and uses Singularity as the container solution.

Invest effort in abstracting data transfer mechanisms for better user experience; while offering different solutions for different use cases, e.g. instant job submission differs from low priority batch processing. Ideally, we would have a joint storage solution which caters both to the cloud and HPC parts of the NOUS platform.

Base the system on proven technologies and practices, like Kubernetes and SLURM and explore supporting multiple container systems which are currently active in the community.

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